

Psychology Methods Blog Feed

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Web page: <http://psychbrief.com/psychological-methods-blog-feed/>

This is the page for an email subscription to a RSS feed that contains many of the best blogs about methods in psychology. You will get an email each time one of these blogs posts an article. All you have to do is follow five simple steps:

1. Go to this website (it's a free email subscription to a RSS feed site): <https://blogtrottr.com/>
2. Copy and paste this hyperlink: "psychbrief.com/psychmethods" (without the quotation marks) into the URL box.
3. Put in your email address.
4. Change the schedule from "Realtime" to however frequently you want updates (there have been a few issues with the shorter time scales so I would suggest selecting "Daily").
5. Click "Feed Me".

Blogs included:

- Hilda Bastian- Absolutely Maybe
- Christina Bergmann & Sho Tsuji- CogTales
- Dorothy Bishop- BishopBlog
- Nick Brown- Nick Brown's Blog
- Lorne Campbell
- Veronika Cheplygina
- Paul Eastwick- Evolving
- Alex Etz- The Etz Files
- Eiko Fried
- Patrick S. Forscher- Persistent Astonishment
- David Funder- Funderstorms
- Andrew Gelman- Statistical Modeling, Causal Inference, and Social Science
- Roger Giner-Sorolla- Approaching Significance
- Olivia Guest- Neuroplausible
- Jessica Hartnett- Not Awful and Boring
- Matti Heino
- Joe Hilgard- Crystal Prison Zone
- Journal of European Psychology Students
- Payton Jones

- Åse Kvist Innes-Ker- Not That Kind of Psychologist
- John K. Kruschke- Doing Bayesian Data Analysis
- Daniel Lakens- The 20% Statistician
- Etienne LeBel- Prove Yourself Wrong
- Alison Ledgerwood- Incurably Nuanced
- Uri Leif, Joe Simmons, & Uri Simonsohn- Data Colada
- Sara Locatelli- Deeply Trivial
- Rich Lucas- The Desk Reject
- Kristoffer Magnusson- R Psychologist
- Deborah G. Mayo- Error Statistics Philosophy
- Personality Interest Group and Espresso (PIG-E)
- PsychBrief
- Jeff Rouder- [Invariances]<http://jeffrouder.blogspot.co.uk/>
- Guillaume Rousselet- Basic Statistics
- John Sakaluk- Sak on Science
- Anne Scheel, Ruben Arslan, Malte Elson, & Julia Rohrer- The 100% CI
- Ulrich Schimmack- Replicability-Index
- Xenia Schmalz- Xenia Schmalz's Blog
- Felix Schönbrodt
- Sam Schwarzkopf- NeuroNeurotic
- Sanjay Srivastava- The Hardest Science
- Ana Todorovic- NeuroAnaTody
- Tim van der Zee- The Skeptical Scientist
- Simine Vazire- Sometimes I'm Wrong
- E.J. Wagenmakers- Bayesian Spectacles
- Dana Wanzer
- Hanne M. Watkins- My Scholarly Goop
- Katherine Wood- Inattentional Coffee
- Tal Yarkoni- citation needed
- Rolf Zwaan